

FORMS OF SOCIAL ASSURANCE

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Abstract

As participants of compulsory state social insurance insurer and the policyholder present Insurer - are legal persons, who carries out mandatory activities on state social insurance and manage insurance funds in accordance with the legislation of Azerbaijan Republic. Insurers - are persons - who acts regardless of the ownership form and legal form or an enterprise with the status of a legal person, that created in accordance with the laws of a foreign state, administrations and organizations, their branches and representative offices, elected organization, as well as, himself or other persons, who realizes social insurance in Azerbaijan Republic.

Keywords: insurance, state, social, legal, assurance, defense, labor, pension, citizen, fund

When we say forms of social assurance - it means imply organizational and legal methods of its implementation. Forms of social assurance used in our republic in modern times, centralized depending on the degree of their centralization and can be classified as local forms. Centralized forms of social assurance include:

- compulsory state social insurance;
- social assurance on expense of budgetary funds;
- mingled form for application of social assurance on special subjects [2].

Although, the state social insurance is indicated as one of the forms of social insurance, but its legal concept wasn't given in the law of February 18, 1977. According to the poin of 18th of Law "On Social Insurance" management of the compulsory state social insurance system is realized by the State Social Defense Fund (SSDF) under the Ministry of Social Defense and Labor of Azerbaijan Republic. Resource of SSDF, which wasn't included to the state and local budgets organizes the financial basis of compulsory state social insurance system. SSPF was created in 1992, as the Pension Fund of Azerbaijan Republic.

Currently, status of the fund has determined by the charter, which was approved by the Decree of Azerbaijan Republic President in June 30, 2020. Compulsory State Social Insurance, State Social Protection Fund and voluntary (additional) social insurance, labor pensions of the population, social benefits, with targeted state social assistance, with pensions and compensations, as well as, the law of Azerbaijan Republic President, and by the acts of Azerbaijan Republic Cabinet of Ministers on areas of dealing other payments (after that - corresponding sphere) acting is a public legal person.

From the SSDF organizational and legal form and from all legal persons, regardless of form of ownership, from individuals engaged in individual entrepreneurial activities (from insurers), as well as, amount determined by law from the policyholder organizes the collection of mandatory state social insurance contributions. It was realized the following payments when a social insurance event occurs about the system of compulsory state social insurance:

- labor pensions;
- benefits for temporary loss of ability to work (for a period determined by law);
- maternity allowance;

- lump sum allowance for the birth of a child;
- allowance for child care until the age established by law;

- funeral allowance;
- full or partial payment of expenses for sanatorium and resort treatment of the insured [1].

Insured persons - who realizes the insurance activity for their favor. The following had been belonged to the person category, which, took part compulsory social insurance with legislative way:

- Decision of the Milli Majlis of Azerbaijan Republic, with the decrees and directions of Azerbaijan Republic President persons appointed functions;
- citizens of Azerbaijan Republic, who works with the contract of employment and stateless persons,
- from sources of Azerbaijan Republic, salary and foreigners, who has got other income from compulsory state social insurance (exploration of oil - gas reserves approving by law, processing and the yields distribution, about export pipelines, working according agreements with contractors and subcontractors, as well as, who is created according to the decision of relevant executive authority, and is engaged in activities of industrial park residence, entered into a contract directly with its contractor and subcontractor, and who was attracted for the purpose of that activity by subcontractor (for 5 years from May 1, 2016), excepting for foreigners);
- working in elective paid appointment, military and person of special rank (temporary active military service - with the exception of military personnel);
- prosecutors, deputy and assistant prosecutors, inspectors of prosecutor's office, tax officials workers;
- members of advocates collegium
- individual entrepreneurship and the persons, who is busy with work activity of physical persons.

Compulsory state social insurance resources is formed mainly from contribution of compulsory state social insurance. According to the item 14 of the law "About Social Insurance" compulsory state social insurance contribution for insurance is the resource, which was given to the insurance company. Insurance premium for compulsory state social insurance determined as a percentage of salary (income) and is paid to the insurer resource account.

All income obtained from hired work, is realized by

state social insurance, as the second centralized form of social insurance after state social insurance at the expense of budget funds. Currently, it is conversing, about taking of resource, for the purposes of social assurance, from the state budget. This organizational and legal form of social assurance, its centralized character is explained in the fact, that types of social assurance and the round of persons, to whom they are provided, clearly defined by law, and they are given assurance by the state. In the same time, expenditures of social financing source also determined on the legislative level.

Currently, to the round of persons, who provided for at the expense of budget funds, are generally not covered by compulsory state social insurance, hasn't any connection with socially useful activities, but provided with certain types of social assurance includes the entire population.

Certain types of social assurance was presented as a member of society without any connection for citizens with work activity. To the such types of assurance include the following: social allowance (excepting social allowance provided from compulsory state social insurance allowance); state social aid; various compensation payments, that provided by law; social services for disabled people at home; semi-inpatient and full inpatient care in social service enterprises ;ensuring employment of disabled people; prosthetic and orthopedic aid; medicine aid; Spa treatment of aged, disabled people and other persons;

keeping children in child care enterprises; various social concession, etc.

Given above, types of social assurance are shown for by law, when social insurance events occur social assurance from budget funds, any other type is presented regardless of, whether it is received or not. Types of social assurance at the expense of budget funds mainly district (city) departments of SSPF healthcare, educational enterprises, employment centers, etc. presented by the authorities.

The third centralized form of social assurance in modern period - although the hybrid form of social assurance appears, it which is typical for still fully functioning forms doesn't have all the signs. At the same time, the state uses from the first and second forms of social assurance, on certain subjects. At this time, as the financial resource, which was given to the persons, who connected with special activity of social assurance, at the same time, it was used both from state social protected fund, and also from the state budget resource. For example, military personnel and labor pension for special pensions of rank.

References

- 1.Kahramanov E., Ahmadov Y. Basics of social work. Baku, "B-print", 2014, 488 p.
- 2.Mammadova S.D. Social state in Azerbaijan: development, perspectives. Baku, "AVRORA" publishing house. 2017, 232 p.